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CONDITIONS FOR BODIES TO BE IN BALANCE

Abstract: The article "Conditions for Bodies to be in Equilibrium" (Conditions for Physical Education) analyzes the conditions necessary for a physical system to reach a state of equilibrium. Equilibrium is a state that occurs when the forces within the system are equal to each other, which is important for physical, mechanical, and biochemical systems. The article discusses the types of equilibrium, such as static and dynamic equilibrium, as well as the external and internal forces necessary to maintain equilibrium, as well as the effect of motion on stability, energy conservation, and system stability. At the same time, the article shows the difference between conditional and true equilibrium states, as well as how this state can be controlled in physical and biological systems.

Keywords: Equilibrium, physical systems, static equilibrium, dynamic equilibrium, equality of forces, biological equilibrium, stability of systems, mechanical equilibrium.

Annotatsiya: "Jismlarning muvozanatda bo'lishi uchun sharoitlar" (Jismoniy tarbiya uchun shart) maqoladagi jismoniy tizimning muvozanat holatiga kelishi uchun zarur bo'lgan shart tahlil qilinadi. Muvozanat - bu tizim ichidagi kuchlar o'zaro tenglashganda yuzaga keladigan holat bo'lib, bu holat jismoniy, mexanik, va biokimyoviy tizimlar

uchun muhim ahamiyatga ega. Maqolada muvozanatning turlari, masalan, statik va dinamik muvozanatlar, shuningdek, muvozanatning saqlanishi uchun zarur bo'lgan tashqi va ichki kuchlar, shuningdek, harakatning turg'unlikka, energiya saqlanishiga va tizimning barqarorligiga ta'siri haqida so'z yuritiladi. Shu bilan birga, maqola shartli va haqiqiy muvozanat holatlari o'rtasidagi farqni, shuningdek, jismoniy va biologik tizimlarda bu holatni qanday boshqarish mumkinligini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Muvozanat, jismoniy tizimlar, statik muvozanat, dinamik muvozanat, kuchlar tengligi, energiya saqlanishi, biologik muvozanat, tizimlar barqarorligi, mexanik muvozanat.

Аннотация: В статье «Условия нахождения тел в равновесии» (условие физического воспитания) анализируется условие, необходимое для нахождения физической системы в состоянии равновесия. Равновесие — это состояние, в котором силы внутри системы уравновешены, и это состояние важно для физических, механических и биохимических систем. В статье рассматриваются виды равновесия, такие как статическое и динамическое равновесие, а также внешние и внутренние силы, необходимые для поддержания равновесия, а также влияние движения на устойчивость, сохранение энергии и устойчивость системы. При этом в статье показано отличие условного и фактического состояний равновесия, а также способы управления этим состоянием в физических и биологических системах.

Ключевые слова: Равновесие, физические системы, статическое равновесие, динамическое равновесие, баланс сил, сохранение энергии, биологическое равновесие, устойчивость систем, механическое равновесие.

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It's easy to take the balance system for granted. Depending on your ability level, you probably don't think twice about standing upright, walking around, and sitting up straight. But while these processes might seem effortless, the reality is that your brain is constantly working to keep your balance system functioning properly. Your brain is responsible for helping you walk, run, and even stand on one foot. But what part of the brain controls balance?

Picture your brain like a factory. There are countless little gears, conveyor belts, and workers milling about, each of them serving a unique purpose to keep you moving through

the world. And while your balance system engages several parts of your brain, the main part of the brain that controls balance is the cerebellum.

In the process of teaching fizik, in the formation of socially active civic competence in students, it is necessary to familiarize students with the events, phenomena and processes taking place in nature and society, the relevant articles of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, pay attention to mental, spiritual-ethical, economic, legal, physical, and labor education. it is necessary to focus, to contribute to the development of the Motherland by mastering a certain profession,

to serve the interests of society and family, to show kindness to people, to encourage them to be generous.

In order to form general cultural competences in students, the teacher should respect the worldview, religious beliefs, national and ethnic characteristics, traditions and rituals of others, respect the historical, spiritual and cultural heritage of the people by instilling national and universal values into the minds and hearts of students and young people when teaching biology. taking care, observing the rules of etiquette established in the society, dressing modestly, following cultural norms and a healthy lifestyle in behavior, aesthetic education along with mental, spiritual-ethical, economic, legal, physical, labor education should pay attention.

Collaborative teaching involves the formation of the following in the student: Teaching each student to daily intense mental work, creative and independent thinking; education of consciousness, independence as a person; to create a sense of personal dignity in each student; strengthening confidence in one's own strength and abilities; Forming a sense of responsibility in education. The technology of cooperative education is based on the understanding that the success of each student in learning leads to the success of the group. and prepares the ground for organizing mutual aid. In the technology of cooperative education, there are several methods of organizing cooperative education of students:

1. Team education (R. Slavin).
2. Collaborative teaching in small groups (R. Slavin, 1986).
3. The "zigzag or saw" method of cooperative teaching (E. Aronson, 1978).
4. "Let's study together" method of cooperative teaching (University of Minnesota professors

- R. Johnson, D. Johnson, 1987).
5. The method of organizing creative research in small groups (developed by the professor of Tel Aviv University in Israel Sh. Sharan 1988).

Teaching in a team (R. Slavin) In teaching in a team, students are divided into two teams of equal number. Both teams perform the same task.

The members of the team work together to complete the educational tasks and pay attention to the acquisition of the knowledge, skills and competences provided for in the subject by each student. R. Slavin said that it is not enough to give instructions to students to complete the tasks in cooperation. It is necessary to create real cooperation among students, to rejoice at the success of each student, to sincerely help each other, and to create a comfortable social and psychological environment. In this technology, when determining the quality of students' knowledge acquisition, they are compared not with each other, but with the previous results of each student. Only then, students will feel responsible and strive to learn more, mastering knowledge, skills and abilities, realizing that the results they have achieved during the lesson will benefit the team.

Collaborative teaching in small groups. In this method, small groups of 4 students are formed. The teacher first explains the topic, then organizes students' independent work. Educational assignments are divided into four parts, and each student performs a certain part of the assignment. At the end of the task, each student thinks about the part he has completed and teaches his friends, then the group members make a general conclusion about the task.

There are 8 forms of cooperation. They consist of the following:

1. Introduction to activity.
2. Independent actions are performed by the teacher and the student in cooperation.
3. The teacher initiates the activity and involves the student in it.
4. Imitative actions (the student who takes a lesson from the teacher acts on the basis of this example).
5. Support actions (the teacher helps the student to choose an intermediate goal and methods of achieving it, and monitors the final result).
6. Self-directed actions (the teacher participates in the assessment of the final result, indicating the common goal).

7. Self-revealing actions.

8. Self-organized actions.

The purpose of cooperative learning activities is to create a control mechanism of mastery activities and joint actions, attitudes and communication. The product of cooperative activity is the emergence of new ideas put forward by students and goals related to the nature of the activity being mastered, and the desire to manage the individual's position in partnership. The method of cooperative activity should be understood as the system of joint actions of the teacher and the student.

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